

Multiple Intelligences Theory on Academic and Licensure Examination Performance among Nursing Graduates: Correlational Study

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Abstract:

The objective of this study is to examine the relationship between multiple intelligences and academic performance in the nursing major subjects and licensure examination for thirty BS Nursing graduates. A relational survey model research was used in the study involving the examination of the existing or potential relationships between two or more variables and analyzing their effects on each other. There were 30 BSN graduates as participants and the data utilized were collected from the Multiple Intelligence Scale administered to the graduates in a form of a questionnaire. The major nursing subjects from first year to fourth year cumulative grades were the bases for academic achievement as well as the licensure

examination results. Descriptive statistics were employed to analyze the data. The multiple intelligence results of the nursing graduates enhanced the academic performance both in theories and skills as observed and practiced in the hospital, clinic, and community. The teachers' use of varied teaching strategies created a positive contribution to the successful performance of the graduates in the nursing licensure examination. The specific intelligence/s that each graduate possesses influenced the level of academic achievement contributing to their wholistic development. The results of the study will guide educators to recognize the importance of considering the learners' multiple intelligences in planning for varied teaching and learning strategies to enhance their academic achievement performance levels. This will also propel more research on the topic focusing on other variables.

Keywords: *Multiple Intelligences Theory, Academic Competence, Licensure Examination.*

Introduction

The world is becoming complicated and intricate that the needs of the modern patients and health care providers must also be upgraded to its highest level of competencies to maintain their relevance and unique value. Consequently, educators need to continuously update and innovate curriculum and instruction to maximize

the learning outcomes and keep students engaged with learning. The higher education institutions in the Philippines aim to promote quality education affirmed through their graduates' performance in licensure examinations and employment profile. Therefore, SMCB, as a Catholic Institution and as the only ISO accredited school in the area finds it extremely necessary to align instructional

delivery based on the 21st century skills, expected graduate attributes and the vision-mission of the institution vis-a-vis the required competencies in the Philippine Nurses Licensure Examination. Thus, this correlational study aimed to establish the relationship between several factors including the graduates' college grade weighted average, PRC official board results, multiple intelligences and learning styles of the graduates in relation to the quality education they get from their Alma Mater. The respondents were thirty successful board examinees in 2023 to 2024 who are now currently employed.

The study revealed a significant and strong correlation between the graduates' weighted grade average in college and PNLE performance. The specific multiple intelligence/s and learning styles of the graduates that were aligned with the teaching styles of the clinical instructors contributed to the graduate's success. For this matter, it is important to understand the different types of learning preferences that the students possess to better study effectively and master difficult nursing concepts. As a matter of fact, specific strategies will not be equally effective for all students, depending on their learning style preference/s. The teachers' awareness of this fact and their creativity and resourcefulness will still play a major role in trying to identify the student's individual leaning strengths and weaknesses.

A number of researchers believe in Howard Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences (MI) which claim that people have eight independent ways of processing information described as follows: Verbal-linguistic: (Word smart); Logical-mathematical: (Logic smart); Visual-spatial: (Picture smart); Auditory-musical: (Music smart); Bodily-kinesthetic: (Body smart); Interpersonal: (People smart); Intrapersonal: (Self smart) and Naturalistic: (Nature smart) (Kirk, 2021)

The eight intelligences as claimed by Gardner are considered abilities and strengths found in the human brain with extremely intricate mechanisms where all these types of "smarts"

work together in a person, each representing different ways of processing information.

One study conducted involving the psychology students revealed that they tend to be more theoretical and abstract, while early childhood and primary education students are more practical. High scores in abstract conceptualization were correlated with a high level of performance on the multiple-choice tests and the relationship between theory and practice. (Maya et al. 2021)

Another study showed that there is a relationship between the types of Intelligence and academic performance by proving that intelligence is a good predictor of academic performance, depending on the type of intelligence or theoretical model utilized as a reference and the culture and nationality of the participants in the study. (Robres et al. 2022)

The teachers, considering the importance of multiple intelligences allow their students to fully develop their potentials. MI particularly emphasizes its application in real life situations. The integration of varied teaching strategies catering to differing intelligences could help teachers assist and enhance students' learning and at the same time expand their abilities beyond subjects complimenting the current teaching styles. (Blasco et al. 2022).

That's why nursing institution like SMCB is seriously engaged in the mission of molding future nurses possessing high morals of honesty, genuine care, and compassion. To constantly maintain and check on this, a specific evaluation tool on the quality objective was formulated in this regard.

The study conducted by Ahvan & Pour (2016), provided evidence that the verbal-linguistic intelligence is the student's most frequent intelligence, and the musical intelligence is the students' least frequent intelligence. This could be due to the opportunities, and the available environment necessary for the nourishment of the mentioned intelligences. It was further attested by the authors that there is a statistically significant relationship between the multiple intelligences and the academic performance

achievement levels of high school students who participated in their study.

Research conducted on the effect of multiple intelligences on the learning motivation and learning environment revealed that the teachers contributed to the full development of the student's potential. This could also have an impact on high-tech industry to develop human resource potential by effectively utilizing the workers' gifted uniqueness. (Lei et al., 2021)

Gardner himself asserts that educators should not employ only one specific theory or educational innovation when designing instruction but instead employ personalized goals and values appropriate to teaching, subject-matter, and student learning needs. Addressing the multiple intelligences can help instructors vary their instruction and methods of assessment and enrich student learning by utilizing personalized instruction (Morgan, 2021).

As recommended by Gardner, uniform or "one size fits all" instruction is detrimental. One alternative for improving the teaching environment is to implement personalized instruction. This involves teaching that matches with the students' interests, anxieties, goals, and strengths without stereotyping them.

Personalized learning involves modifying students' learning experiences according to their individual needs, skills, and interests. It allows them to follow an optimal learning strategy based on various types of instructional methods, which include group projects, instructional software, and individual and small-group sessions with teachers. This approach differs from the traditional way of teaching, which emphasizes leading the whole class to learn a common lesson (Childress & Benson, 2014).

It has been proven that children whose parents have demonstrated consistent and rational rule enforcement throughout their upbringing perform better both academically and socially, and this may explain for the success shown by children of older parents. The stability of personality traits that middle-aged parents seem

to display has a strong positive impact on their children. (Melamed, 2021)

With the intricacies, dynamism, and challenging roles of nurses, this requires constant updating, learning and improvement to ensure the stability of high standards of practice and nursing competence.

A study done on the multiple intelligences among nursing students attested that critical thinking disposition is significantly associated with MI and recommend that this should be considered to enhance teaching the nursing students. (Kwang & Shi, 2014)

That is why SMCB painstakingly works annually for its quality assurance through ISO certification and PAASCU accreditation to maintain its high standards of educational services.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to determine the effect of nursing graduates' multiple intelligences and influence of their learning styles in terms of:

- a) academic achievements in major nursing subjects and
- b) successful performance in nursing licensure examinations

Methodology

This is a correlational study which is a type of research design that looks on the relationships between two or more variables. Correlational studies are non-experimental, which means that there was no manipulation or control on the variables.

Research Design

Data were analyzed by descriptive statistics, Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient and multiple regression analysis.

Research Site

This involved a private non-sectarian accredited nursing school that has been existing for more than 100 years.

Respondents

The participants of the study were 20 females, and 10 males new BS Nursing graduates who are currently employed as registered nurses either in hospitals, clinics, and local/foreign communities.

Instrumentation

The data were gathered utilizing the multiple intelligence scales, survey questionnaire and the official nursing licensure results obtained from the Professional Regulation Commission.

Research Ethics Protocol

The present study was conducted in accordance with the guidelines set forth by SMCB Ethics

Committee. Written informed consent was obtained from all the participants after thorough reading and approval of the ethical consent form prior to participation in the study. The participants were also asked to follow the research guidelines. The research protocol was approved by the Ethical Committee of the institution.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation of PNLE general average and multiple intelligences of thirty nursing graduates.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics for PNLE General Average and Multiple Intelligences

	Mean	SD	N
PNLE General Average	81.09	2.55	30
Verbal-Linguistic	2.87	0.86	30
Logical-Mathematical	2.83	0.79	30
Visual-Spatial	3.37	0.85	30
Bodily Kinesthetic	2.57	0.90	30
Musical	2.77	0.90	30
Interpersonal	2.87	0.63	30
Intrapersonal	3.03	0.77	30
Naturalist	3.50	0.63	30

The table reveals that the mean of PNLE general average was 81.09 with standard deviation of 2.55. Among the eight multiple intelligences, naturalist has the highest mean of 3.50 with a standard deviation of 0.63. On the other hand, bodily kinesthetic has the lowest mean of 2.57 with a standard deviation of 0.90.

Table 2 (Appendix) presents the results of multiple linear regression analysis which were performed to determine the relationship between the PNLE general average and multiple intelligences of thirty nursing graduates.

Tabulated findings show that there is a significant correlation that was found between PNLE general average and logical-mathematical ($p=0.49$). This significant relationship was manifested by the computed probability values for these variables which is less than the 0.05 significance level.

Table 3 displays the mean and standard deviation of PNLE general average and learning styles of thirty nursing graduates.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics for PNLE General Average and Nursing Graduates' Learning Styles

	Mean	SD	N
PNLE General Average	81.09	2.55	30
Visual	3.43	0.68	30
Auditory	3.20	0.48	30
Tactual	2.90	0.48	30
Kinesthetic	2.63	0.93	30

The findings imply that logical-mathematical intelligence has significant effect on the licensure examination performance among nursing graduates.

In accordance with the above findings the study of Shirawia et al. (2023) on the Logical Mathematical Intelligence and its Impact on the Academic Achievement for Math Teachers found a significant effect between the logical-mathematical intelligence of the female students, and the overall academic achievement in mathematics.

The table reveals that the mean of PNLE general average was 81.09 with standard deviation of 2.55. Among the learning styles of thirty nursing graduates, visual has the highest mean of 3.43 with a standard deviation of 0.68 while kinesthetic has the lowest mean of 2.63 with a standard deviation of 0.93.

Table 4 (Appendix) shows the results of multiple linear regression analysis which were performed to determine the relationship between the PNLE general average and learning styles of thirty nursing graduates.

Indicated from the table that no significant relationship was found between PNLE general average and learning styles of thirty nursing graduates.

The results imply that learning styles have no significant effect on the licensure examination performance among nursing graduates.

The findings agreed with the work of Oliveira et al. (2023), the authors attested that to maximize the effect of learning style that will give more opportunities for learning better is a personal choice of the learner and it does not guarantee a maximum academic performance. However, it is important to note that there is no direct relationship between learning styles and academic performance. Some studies suggest that different learning styles may be effective or not effective in different contexts or subjects.

Table 5 exhibits the results of the mean and standard deviation of PNLE general average and average on major nursing subjects of nursing graduates.

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics for PNLE General Average and Major Nursing Subjects

	Mean	SD	N
PNLE General Average	81.09	2.55	30
Theoretical Foundations in Nursing	86.13	4.39	30
Health Assessment	84.77	3.39	30
Health Education	87.43	3.89	30
Fundamentals of Nursing Practice	86.93	4.41	30
Community Health Nursing 1	85.83	4.50	30
Nutrition and Diet Therapy	85.60	4.08	30
Pharmacology	87.90	4.96	30
Care of Mother, Child, Adolescentwell client	86.87	4.01	30

Health Care Ethics (Bioethics)	86.93	4.23	30
Care of Mother, Child at Risk	87.17	4.44	30
Nursing Informatics	90.83	4.20	30
Nursing Research 1	86.10	3.02	30
Care of Clients with Problems in Oxygenation etc.	86.00	3.38	30
Community Health Nursing 2	89.23	4.65	30
Care of Older Adults	86.50	3.82	30
Nursing Research 2	88.03	4.63	30
Care of clients with problems in Nutrition etc.	87.03	3.61	30
Care of Clients with Maladaptive Patterns of Behavior (acute & chronic)	88.53	3.75	30
Care of Clients with Life-Threatening Conditions etc.	87.47	4.58	30
Nursing Leadership & Management	88.40	3.49	30
Disaster Nursing	89.07	3.97	30
Intensive Nursing Practicum (hospital/community)	86.40	4.09	30

The table presents that the mean of PNLE general average was 81.09 with standard deviation of 2.55. Among the major subjects of thirty nursing graduates, nursing informatics received the highest mean of 90.83 with a standard deviation of 4.20. On the other hand, health assessment got the lowest mean of 84.77 with a standard deviation of 3.39.

Table 6 displays the results of multiple linear regression analysis which were performed to determine the relationship between the PNLE general average and average on major nursing subjects of nursing graduates.

Table 6. Regression Coefficients (a) for PNLE General Average and Major Nursing Subjects

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	53.926	9.116		5.915	0.000	35.252	72.600
	Care of Mother, Child, Adolescent well client	0.313	0.105	0.491	2.983*	0.006	0.098	0.528
Excluded Variables ^a								
Model		Beta In	t	Sig.	Partial Correlation	Collinearity Statistics		
							Tolerance	
1	Theoretical Foundations in	.118 ^b	0.647(ns)	0.523	0.124	0.831		
	Health Assessment	.290 ^b	1.619(ns)	0.117	0.298	0.798		
	Health Education	.124 ^b	0.568(ns)	0.575	0.109	0.578		
	Fundamentals of Nursing Practice	.282 ^b	1.344(ns)	0.190	0.250	0.598		
	Community Health Nursing 1	.043 ^b	0.204(ns)	0.840	0.039	0.626		

Nutrition and Diet Therapy	.053 ^b	0.149(ns)	0.883	0.029	0.225
Pharmacology	-.370 ^b	-1.410(ns)	0.170	-0.262	0.380
Health Care Ethics (Bioethics)	.167 ^b	0.793(ns)	0.435	0.151	0.619
Care of Mother, Child at Risk	-.196 ^b	-0.803(ns)	0.429	-0.153	0.459
Nursing Informatics	-.291 ^b	-1.660(ns)	0.109	-0.304	0.828
Nursing Research 1	.033 ^b	0.177(ns)	0.861	0.034	0.824
Care of Clients with Problems in Oxygenation etc.	-.100 ^b	-0.545(ns)	0.590	-0.104	0.832
Community Health Nursing 2	-.240 ^b	-1.145(ns)	0.262	-0.215	0.611
Care of Older Adults	-.019 ^b	-0.089(ns)	0.929	-0.017	0.627
Nursing Research 2	-.033 ^b	-0.152(ns)	0.881	-0.029	0.576
Care of clients with problems in Nutrition etc.	-.104 ^b	-0.384	0.704(ns)	-0.074	0.379
Care of Clients with Maladaptive Patterns of Behavior (acute	.099 ^b	0.451	0.655(ns)	0.087	0.574
Care of Clients with Life-Threatening Conditions etc.	-.164 ^b	-0.891	0.381(ns)	-0.169	0.807
Nursing Leadership & Management	-.123 ^b	-0.560	0.580(ns)	-0.107	0.574
Disaster Nursing	-.308 ^b	-1.733	0.094(ns)	-0.316	0.801
Intensive Nursing Practicum (hosp./community)	.123 ^b	0.610	0.547(ns)	0.117	0.676

Note: a - Dependent Variable: PNLE General Average; Predictors in the Model: (Constant), Care of Mother, Child, Adolescent-well client

Elucidated from the table that a significant correlation was found between PNLE general average and care of mother, child, and adolescent-well client ($p=0.006$). This significant relationship was manifested by the computed probability values for these variables which is less than the 0.05 significance level.

The findings imply that care of mother, child, and adolescent has a significant contribution on the licensure examination performance among nursing graduates.

The findings agreed with the statement made by the National Institutes of Health (2023) that

maternal health care is essential not only to the mothers and babies but also to the general welfare of society. Nurses play a vital role in promoting maternal health, to help address the challenges mothers face in accessing quality health care and leading healthier lives.

Table 7 presents the results of the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient analysis which was performed to determine the relationship between the PNLE general average and average on major nursing subjects of nursing graduates.

Table 7. The Correlation Analysis on the Relationship between the PNLE General Average and Major Nursing Subjects

		Major Nursing Subjects	PNLE General Average
Major Nursing Subjects	Pearson Correlation	1	.364*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.48
	N	30	30
PNLE General Average	Pearson Correlation	.364*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.48	
	N	30	30

Note: *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Tabulated findings show that there is a significant correlation found between PNLE general average and average on major nursing subjects of nursing graduates.

The results imply that major nursing subjects have significant effect on the licensure examination performance among nursing graduates.

The findings agreed with the work of Guillermo et al. (2024), whose study identified significant relationships between nursing major subjects such as, Health Assessment, Disaster Nursing, Care of Older Adult and Psychiatric Nursing, indicating that higher academic performance in these subjects correlated with better board exam performance.

Conclusion

These conclusions were made in consideration of the findings.

- The results revealed that among the eight multiple intelligences, naturalist has the highest mean of 3.50 with a standard deviation of 0.63 while bodily kinesthetic has the lowest mean of 2.57 with a standard deviation of 0.90.
- Tabulated findings displayed that there is a significant correlation that was found between PNLE general average and logical-mathematical ($p=0.49$).
- The results imply that learning styles have no significant effect on the licensure examination performance among nursing graduates.

- There is a significant correlation found between PNLE general average and care of mother, child, and adolescent clients ($p=0.006$).
- There is a significant correlation found between PNLE general average and average on major nursing subjects of nursing graduates.
- Therefore, it is really very important to motivate the nursing students on the importance of regular attendance on the lectures to gain the basic concepts of the major nursing subjects and seriously focus on the board review to pass the nurses board exam with flying colors to become licensed to work. The contributing factors of knowing one's type of intelligence and utilize it to the fullest can serve as a passport to excel in the nursing profession.

Recommendations

The findings of the study shed light on the importance of providing quality nursing education to promote top performance in the board examinations in the light of the significant contribution of other factors and strategies in terms of multiple intelligences, learning styles, teaching styles, and grade weighted average in major nursing subjects. Therefore, the following recommendations may be helpful:

- Formulation of an effective Annual Curriculum Development Plan with the participation of partner agencies and stakeholders.
- Organize NEP or Knowledge Enhancement Program to help those

academically challenged students to improve their grades.

- Regular in-service training, seminars and conferences should be availed by the faculty to update and upgrade their teaching strategies
- Formulate e-tools for teachers and students to evaluate the effectiveness of the curriculum and instruction as well as the Quality Objectives of the College Department
- The clinical instructors should continuously enhance the nursing lectures by giving more relevant and innovative classroom experiences, immersion and benchmarking to first class hospitals here and abroad.
- Intensify the in-house review by inviting expert guest lecturers from other institutions.

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Appendix

Table 2. Regression Coefficients (a) for PNLE General Average and Multiple Intelligences

Coefficients ^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF
1	Constant	75.545	1.830		41.274	0.000	71.795	79.294					
	Logical- Mathematical	1.281	0.623	0.362	2.056*	0.049	0.005	2.557	0.362	0.362	0.362	1.000	1.000

Excluded Variables ^a

Model		Beta In	t	Sig.	Partial Correlation	Collinearity Statistics		
						Tolerance	VIF	Minimum Tolerance
1	Verbal- Linguistic	.209 ^b	1.081(ns)	0.289	0.204	0.822	1.217	0.822
	Visual-Spatial	.088 ^b	0.372(ns)	0.713	0.071	0.568	1.762	0.568
	Bodily Kinesthetic	-.080 ^b	-0.413(ns)	0.683	-0.079	0.855	1.169	0.855
	Musical	-.092 ^b	-0.453(ns)	0.654	-0.087	0.772	1.295	0.772
	Interpersonal	-.127 ^b	-0.639(ns)	0.528	-0.122	0.807	1.238	0.807
	Intrapersonal	.190 ^b	0.986(ns)	0.333	0.186	0.833	1.200	0.833
	Naturalist	.063 ^b	0.326(ns)	0.747	0.063	0.855	1.169	0.855

Note: a - Dependent Variable: PNLE GENERAL AVERAGE; b - Predictors in the Model: (Constant), Logical-Mathematical

Table 4. Regression Coefficients (a) for PNLE General Average and Nursing Graduates' Learning Styles

Model		Coefficients ^a											
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	77.664	4.478		17.345	0.000	68.442	86.886					
	Visual	-0.506	1.244	-0.123	-0.407	0.688	-3.068	2.056	0.162	-0.081	-	0.404	2.478
	Auditory	-1.221	1.510	-0.211	-0.808	0.427	-4.332	1.890	0.009	-0.160	-	0.538	1.859
	Tactual	2.271	2.083	0.390	1.090	0.286	-2.020	6.562	0.234	0.213	0.209	0.287	3.484
	Kinesthetic	0.215	0.698	0.071	0.308	0.760	-1.223	1.654	0.169	0.062	0.059	0.686	1.458
2	(Constant)	77.495	4.366		17.749	0.000	68.521	86.470					
	Visual	-0.430	1.198	-0.104	-0.359	0.722	-2.893	2.033	0.162	-0.070	-	0.420	2.382
	Auditory	-1.197	1.482	-0.207	-0.808	0.427	-4.243	1.849	0.009	-0.156	-	0.539	1.854
	Tactual	2.409	1.999	0.414	1.205	0.239	-1.700	6.518	0.234	0.230	0.227	0.301	3.323
3	(Constant)	76.758	3.790		20.251	0.000	68.981	84.535					
	Auditory	-0.933	1.266	-0.161	-0.737	0.467	-3.531	1.664	0.009	-0.140	-	0.716	1.398
	Tactual	1.863	1.275	0.320	1.460	0.156	-0.754	4.479	0.234	0.271	0.271	0.716	1.398
4	(Constant)	75.226	3.144		23.928	0.000	68.786	81.666					
	Tactual	1.361	1.070	0.234	1.272	0.214	-0.831	3.553	0.234	0.234	0.234	1.000	1.000
5	(Constant)	79.173	0.511		154.937	0.000	78.128	80.218					

Note: a - Dependent Variable: PNLE GENERAL AVERAGE